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PECULIARITIES OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN EARLY CHILDREN WITH NON-SOCIAL PNEUMONIA LIVING IN ECOLOGICAL REGIONS.

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ABSTRACT

The ecology and health of the population of the Aral Sea region is an urgent problem not only for Uzbekistan, but also for the entire world community. The unfavorable environmental situation has placed a heavy burden on the entire population of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, but children are especially affected, since the children's body, due to the functional immaturity of tissues and adaptation and protection systems, is especially sensitive to the influence of environmental factors. Environmental changes in the Aral Sea region affect the health of the younger generation in many ways; this is an increased incidence of respiratory diseases, among which acute respiratory infections, bronchitis and pneumonia take the first place.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), pneumonia is the most common cause of death in children in the world, in particular, it accounts for 17.5% of the mortality rate in children under 5 years of age, annually killing approximately 1.1 million children in this age group (WHO, 2016).

The prevalence of pneumonia among children and adolescents in the Republic of Uzbekistan ranges from 17.7% to 19.5%. Studies have shown that the examined children with community-acquired pneumonia show pronounced changes in intercellular immune mechanisms, which are manifested by impaired production of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, which depends on environmentally unfavorable living conditions. To study the level of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) in children living in different ecological regions (using the example of Khorezm and Tashkent). 55 children with acute community-acquired pneumonia aged from 1 year to 3 years living in different regional conditions, of which 35 sick children (main group), permanently residing in the Aral Sea region (in the Khorezm region) and 20 children with community-acquired pneumonia (comparison group), living in Tashkent. The control groups consisted of 20 practically healthy children permanently residing in the Aral Sea region (in the Khorezm region) and 20 children with community-acquired pneumonia living in Tashkent. The average age of children in the main group was 1.95 ± 0.14 years, while the average age in the comparison group was 2.19 ± 0.21 years. The frequency of occurrence of boys in the main group was 40%, and girls - 60%; in the comparison group, boys and girls were observed in 50% of cases, respectively.

Verification of the diagnosis was carried out according to the classification of the main clinical forms of bronchopulmonary diseases in children, approved at a special meeting of the XVIII National Congress on Respiratory Diseases (2009). In 100% of cases, the diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia was verified by chest radiography

Key words: community-acquired pneumonia, cytokine status, children, ecology Aral sea, environmental environment.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЦИТОКИНОВОГО СТАТУСА У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА ВНЕБОЛЬНИЧНОЙ ПНЕВМОНИЕЙ, ПРОЖИВАЮЩИХ В ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ РЕГИОНАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Экология и здоровье населения Приаралья актуальная проблема не только для Узбекистана, но и всей мировой общественности. Неблагополучие экологической обстановки тяжелым грузом легло на все население Республики Каракалпакстан, но особенно страдают дети, так как детский организм в связи с функциональной незрелостью тканей и систем адаптации и защиты особо чувствителен к влиянию факторов окружающей среды. Изменения экологии в регионе Приаралья отражается на здоровье подрастающего поколения во многом, это повышенная заболеваемость органов дыхания, среди которых на первое место выходят ОРЗ, бронхиты и пневмонии. По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ) пневмония является наиболее частой причиной смерти детей в мире, в частности, в структуре смертности детей до 5 лет она составляет 17,5%, ежегодно унося жизни примерно 1,1 миллиона детей этой возрастной группы (ВОЗ, 2016). Распространённость пневмоний среди детей и подростков в Республики Узбекистан составляет от 17,7% до 19,5%.

Проведенные исследования показали, что у обследованных детей с внебольничной пневмонией отмечаются выраженные изменения в межклеточных иммунных механизмах, которые проявляются нарушением продукции про воспалительных и противовоспалительных цитокинов, которое зависит от экологически неблагоприятных условий проживания. Изучить уровень про- и противовоспалительных цитокинов при внебольничной пневмонии (ВП) у детей, проживающих в разных экологических регионах (на примере Хорезма и Ташкента). Были исследованы 55 детей с острой внебольничной пневмонией в возрасте от 1 года до 3-х лет проживающих в разных региональных условиях, из них 35 больных детей (основная группа), постоянно проживающих регионе Аральского моря (на территории Хорезмской области) и 20 детей с внебольничной пневмонией (группа сравнения), проживающих в г. Ташкенте. Группы контроля составили 20 практически здоровых детей, постоянно проживающих регионе Аральского моря (на территории Хорезмской области) и 20 детей с внебольничной пневмонией, проживающих в г. Ташкенте.

Средний возраст детей в основной группе составил $1,95 \pm 0,14$ лет, тогда как средний возраст в группе сравнения – $2,19 \pm 0,21$ лет. Частота встречаемость мальчиков в основной группе составила 40%, а девочек -60%, в группе сравнения мальчики и девочки наблюдались в 50% случаях соответственно.

Верификация диагноза проводилась по классификации основных клинических форм бронхолегочных заболеваний у детей, одобренной на специальном заседании XVIII Национального конгресса по болезням органов дыхания (2009). В 100% случаев диагноз внебольничная пневмония был верифицирован путем рентгенографии органов грудной клетки.

Ключевые слова: внебольничная пневмония, цитокиновый статус, дети, экология, Аральского моря, окружающей среды.

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NOQULAY EKOLOGIK MUHITDA YASHOVCHI ERTA YOSHLI BOLALARDA SHIFOXONADAN TASHQARI ZOTILJAMDA SITOKIN HOLATINING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Orol bo'yi xududi ekologiyasi va aholisining salomatligi nafaqat O'zbekiston, balki butun jahon jamoatchiligi uchun ham dolzarb muammodir. Ekologik vaziyatning noqulayligi Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasining barcha aholisiga og'ir yuk bo'ldi, lekin ayniqsa bu holatdan bolalar aziyat chekmoqda, chunki moslashuv va himoya to'qima tizimlarining funksional etilmaganligi tufayli bolalar organizmi atrof-muhit omillarining ta'siriga juda sezgir. Orolbo'yi mintaqasidagi ekologik o'zgarishlar ko'p jihatdan o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlod salomatligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda, bu nafas olish a'zolarining kasallanish darajasining yuqoriligiga olib kelmoqda va ular orasida O'RK, bronxit va zotiljam kasalliklari birinchi o'rinni egallamoqda. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, zotiljam dunyodagi bolalar o'limining eng keng tarqalgan sababi bo'lib, 5 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalar o'limi ko'rsatkichining 17,5% ni tashkil etadi va har yili shu yoshdagi taxminan 1,1 million bolani (JSST, 2016) hayotdan olib ketadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida bolalar va o'smirlar o'rtasida zotiljam kasalligining tarqalishi 17,7% dan 19,5% gacha tashkil etadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'tkir pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan bolalarda hujayralararo immunitet mexanizmlarida sezilarli o'zgarishlar mavjud bo'lib, ular atrof-muhitning noqulay yashash sharoitlariga bog'liq bo'lgan yallig'lanishga qarshi va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning ishlab chiqarilishining buzilishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi.

Turli ekologik mintaqalarda yashovchi bolalarda (Xorazm va Toshkent misolida) shifoxonadan tashqari pnevmoniyada yallig'lanishga qarshi va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar darajasini o'rganish. 1 yoshdan-3 yoshgacha 55 nafar o'tkir pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan bolalar. Turli hududiy sharoitlarda yashab, shundan 35 nafar bemor (asosiy guruh), Orolbo'yida (Xorazm viloyatida) doimiy yashovchi va 20 nafari o'tkir pnevmoniya bilan og'rigan bolalar (qiyoslash guruhi), Toshkent shahrida yashovchi. Nazorat guruhlari Orolbo'yida (Xorazm viloyatida) doimiy yashovchi 20 nafar amalda sog'lom bolalar va Toshkent shahrida yashovchi 20 nafar o'tkir pnevmoniya bilan kasallangan bolalardan iborat edi. Asosiy guruhdagi bolalarning o'rtacha yoshi $1,95 \pm 0,14$ yil bo'lsa, taqqoslash guruhidagi bolalarning o'rtacha yoshi $2,19 \pm 0,21$ yoshni tashkil qildi. Asosiy guruhda o'g'il bolalarning chastotasi 40%, qizlar esa - 60%; taqqoslash guruhida mos ravishda 50% hollarda o'g'il bolalar va qizlar kuzatilgan. Tashxisni tekshirish nafas olish kasalliklari bo'yicha XVIII Milliy Kongressning maxsus yig'ilishida tasdiqlangan bolalarda bronxopulmoner kasalliklarning asosiy klinik shakllari tasnifiga muvofiq amalga oshirildi (2009). 100% hollarda o'tkir pnevmoniya tashxisi ko'krak qafasi rentgenogrammasi bilan tasdiqlangan.

Kalit suzlar: shifoxonadan tashqari zotiljam, sitokin holati, bolalar, ekologiya. Orol bo'yi, atrof-muhit.

Community-acquired pneumonia in pediatric patients is considered to be one of the Actual's problem, especially the formation of its protracted course. In recent years, we have achieved some success in the diagnosis is, and treating and nosocomial pneumonia in children, causing the disease has changed, also reduced the number of severe, leading to a lowering w mortality in this disease. However, despite all the measures, the incidence of nosocomial pneumonia is quite high, especially among the child population [3, 4, 5, 13].

The impact of a complex of extreme climatogeographic, social, environmental factors is reflected in unfavorable dynamic shifts in the health of children [2, 8, 9]

The study of inflammation markers at the present stage is given a lot of attention, especially when the impact of ecological trouble, and in particular in the diagnosis ie pneumonia [7, 11]. Among the markers of inflammation, a special place belongs to cytokines. The study of the level

of cytokines in children is carried out in order to predict the course of community-acquired pneumonia, as well as early diagnosis [1, 8, 10] .

All of the above dictates the expediency of studying a comprehensive assessment of the severity of community-acquired pneumonia in young children , as well as the development of prognostic criteria for the development of a severe course at the earlier stages of hospitalization of a child.

Purpose of the study : to study the level of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) in children living in different ecological regions (by the example of Khorezm and Tashkent) .

Materials and methods of research : 55 children with acute community-acquired pneumonia aged 1 to 3 years living in different regional conditions were studied , of which 35 sick children (main group) , permanently residing in the Aral Sea region (in the Khorezm region) and 20 children with community-acquired pneumonia (comparison group) living in Tashkent. The control groups consisted of 20 practically healthy children permanently residing in the Aral Sea region (in the Khorezm region) and 20 children with community-acquired pneumonia living in Tashkent.

The average age of children in the main group was 1.95 ± 0.14 years, while the average age in the comparison group was 2.19 ± 0.21 years. The frequency of occurrence of boys in the main group was 40%, and for girls - 60%; in the comparison group, boys and girls were observed in 50% of cases, respectively.

The diagnosis was verified according to the classification of the main clinical forms of bronchopulmonary diseases in children, approved at a special meeting of the XVIII National Congress on Respiratory Diseases (2009). In 100% of cases, the diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia was verified by chest X-ray.

Inclusion criteria : age from 1 to 3 years; informed consent; clinically and radiologically confirmed community-acquired pneumonia, absence of concomitant bacterial infections.

Exclusion criteria : non-compliance with inclusion criteria; the presence of chronic respiratory diseases (bronchial asthma); a history of repeated cases of pneumonia, malformations of the bronchopulmonary system.

By ontsentratsi w cytokines - IL - 1, IL -4, IL -6 and TNF- α was determined by ELISA using test systems Vector-Best (Novosibirsk, Russia) .

To assess the reference values, a control group was created, consisting of 20 apparently healthy children of the same age and gender.

The studies were carried out when the child was admitted to a hospital.

Statistical studies were carried out using the Excel- 2007 software according to the generally accepted method.

Results of the study : the main risk factors for the development of community-acquired pneumonia in patients living in ecologically unfavorable regions was a premorbid background. Analysis of the data obtained showed that 89.1% of children admitted to inpatient treatment had concomitant diseases . In this case, rickets were diagnosed in 80.0% of children, protein- energy deficiency of PEM - in 62.9% of children, anemia - in 97.1% of children . Whereas in children from Tashkent, the burden of premorbid background was recorded in 65% of children, which is 24.1% lower than in children from Khorezm.

The severity of the condition of children upon admission of races was assessed as moderately severe - in 48.6% of cases in the main group and as severe - in 51.4% of cases, in the comparison group 45% of children were admitted to a serious condition, and in moderately severe - 55%. Children from Khorezm were more often admitted to the hospital in a serious condition in relation to children living in Tashkent, however, there was no reliability between the data ($P > 0.05$).

Focal pneumonia was more common in the study group (71.4% versus 55%, respectively), while segmental pneumonia was less common (25.7% versus 30%, respectively), but the indicators were not reliable (Table 1) . Most often in the comparison group, lobar pneumonia is recorded (15%), while in the main group its percentage was 2.9% ($P < 0.05$). In children of the Khorezm region,

bilateral pneumonia was observed significantly more often during examination (42.9% versus 20%; $P < 0.05$).

Table 1

Characteristics of the examined children with community-acquired pneumonia

	Main group (n = 35)		Comparison group (n = 20)	
	n	%	n	%
Condition upon admission:				
moderate (n /%)	18	51.4	nine	45
severe (n /%)	17	48.6	eleven	55
Focal pneumonia (n /%)	25	71.4	eleven	55
Segmental pneumonia (n /%)	nine	25.7	6	thirty
Lobar pneumonia (n /%)	one	2.9	3	fifteen
Unilateral pneumonia (n /%)	twenty	57.1	sixteen	80
Bilateral pneumonia (n /%)	fifteen	42.9	4	twenty

Objective examination in children of the main group showed pronounced symptoms of intoxication and respiratory failure, which were characterized by hyperthermic syndrome (average body temperature $39.9 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$), hyperventilation with an average respiratory rate of 77.2 ± 0.2 per minute. A wet cough was noted in 85.7% of children.

In 100% of the main group, pallor of the skin with a pronounced marble tint and cyanosis of the nasolabial triangle was noted.

The participation of auxiliary muscles in the act of breathing with retraction of the compliant areas of the chest occurred in 98.2%.

Auscultation in 78.2% of cases over the affected areas of the lungs heard dry fine bubbly moist rales.

The boundaries of relative cardiac dullness were somewhat expanded in 65.5% of cases, manifestations of sinus tachycardia occurred in 82.9% of patients.

It should be noted that in all 17 children of the main group with a symptomatic complex of severe pneumonia with manifestation of microcirculatory disorders, all cases were accompanied by bleeding from the injection sites.

Two-thirds of the children had obvious oliguria (70.3%), and in one-third of the patients, the daily urine volume was significantly reduced (less than 52%).

In 14 (40.0%) children of the main group, extravasates of a hemorrhagic nature were revealed, which, as a rule, was combined with bloody vomit in the form of coffee grounds and tarry stools. One child had hemorrhage into the conjunctiva, and two children (8.6%) had epistaxis.

All children of the comparison group showed symptoms of intoxication, accompanied by an increase in temperature from $38.8 \pm 0.5^{\circ} \text{C}$ in combination with manifestations of microcirculatory disorders in the form of pallor of the skin with a marble tint (100%). Intoxication syndrome was accompanied by severe respiratory failure with an increase in respiratory rate in 85% of cases.

In 3/4 of the patients, cyanosis of the nasolabial triangle was observed. In 2/3 of the patients in this group, fine -bubbling moist rales were heard auscultation at the height of inspiration.

A change from the side of the cardiovascular system in the form of some muffling of heart sounds was observed in 85% of patients, and in 95.0% there was a manifestation of sinus tachycardia. From the urinary system in almost all patients (97.1%) had the phenomenon of oliguria with a decrease in daily urine output in the range of 62.0% to 74.0%.

It should be noted the aforementioned symptoms of intoxication, respiratory failure with manifestations of stasis on the skin (marble shade), in 55.0% of cases there was bleeding from the injection sites.

Bloody vomiting in the form of coffee grounds was observed in 25.0% of children, tarry stools were observed in 1/4 of the patients.

In the general blood analysis of patients in the comparison group with pneumonia, the number of erythrocytes was within $3.9 \times 10^{12} / l$, hemoglobin ($107.5 \pm 1.1 \text{ g} / l$), leukocytes ($10.1 \pm 0.6 \times 10^9 /$

l) with stab shift ($10.5 \pm 0.1\%$), ESR (17.5 ± 1.1 mm / h), which indicates a tendency to anemia, leukocytosis, accelerated erythrocyte sedimentation rate in this category of children.

The gemmogram in children of the main group showed a clear tendency to anemization (Er $3.15 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{12} / l$; HB 89.5 ± 1.3 g / l), leukocytosis ($15.3 \pm 0.3 \times 10^9 / l$) with a noticeable stab shift ($28.5 \pm 1.1\%$) and an acceleration of ESR (29.5 ± 1.2 mm / h).

The revealed changes in the peripheral blood of an infectious and inflammatory nature in patients from the comparison group were moderate, and in patients of the main group they were more significant.

As a result, we found that children in both the main group and the comparison group had an imbalance in the cytokine status, which depended on an unfavorable environmental situation.

table 2

The level of cytokines in the examined children with CAP in a comparative aspect (M ±m)

Indicator	Control group (n = 20)	Main group (n = 35)	Comparison group (n = 20)
IL-1	1.24 ± 0.12	$35.3 \pm 5.0^{**}$	$25.1 \pm 1.1^{** \wedge}$
IL-4	4.71 ± 0.12	$20.3 \pm 1.3^{**}$	$9.3 \pm 2.4^{**}$
IL-6	$6,74 \pm 0,18$	$37.5 \pm 6.7^{**}$	$14.8 \pm 2.3^{* \wedge}$
TNFα	3.8 ± 0.9	$102.9 \pm 10.6^{**}$	$27.1 \pm 2.4^{** \wedge}$

Note : * - the difference relative to the data of the control group is significant (** - $P < 0.001$), ^ - the reliability of the data among the groups of children with community-acquired pneumonia (^ - $P < 0.05$).

IL-1 is involved in the triggering process of the immune response, is key in the development of inflammation, and is involved in the regulation of hematopoiesis. IL-1 is a pro-inflammatory cytokine [15].

As can be seen from the table, a sharp increase in it was established in children with community-acquired pneumonia in relation to the control data both in the main group and in the comparison group (1.24 ± 0.12 pg / ml versus 35.3 ± 5.4 pg / ml and 25.1 ± 4.9 pg / ml, respectively; $P < 0.001$). The influence of the ecological disadvantage in which children with community-acquired pneumonia live (Khorezm city) was also established, so IL-1 in this cohort of children was significantly higher than in children from Tashkent (35.3 ± 5.4 pg / ml and 25.1 ± 4.9 pg / ml, respectively; $P < 0.05$).

IL6 is a mediator of the acute phase of inflammation [12]; in our study, this interleukin was markedly high in children with pneumonia in both groups in relation to control values ($P < 0.001$). Among children with pneumonia of Khorezm, its 2.5-fold increase was established in relation to the indicators of children in Tashkent (37.5 ± 6.7 pg / ml versus 14.8 ± 2.3 pg / ml, respectively; $P < 0.05$) ...

TNFα triggers the body's immune response to any external stimulus, in our case, inflammation, and affects blood coagulation rates. TNF-alpha in the blood of a healthy child is determined in low concentrations from 0 to 8 pg / ml and acts as a hormone that has a pyrogenic effect [14].

Indicators of TNF-alpha in children with pneumonia significantly increased relative to the control group ($P < 0.05$). In children of the main group, this indicator had significant values for an increase in comparison with the comparison group (27.1 ± 2.4 pg / ml versus 102.9 ± 10.6 pg / ml; $P < 0.01$).

IL4 is a pro - inflammatory interlicin , its increase has a key role in the pathogenesis of pneumonia by stimulating its procoagulant activity, and leads to cytokine- mediated lung damage [6] . IL4 indicators in children with community-acquired pneumonia in our study have a significant increase in relation to the control group, especially in children of the main group, where the indicator increases almost 27 times in relation to the control group ($P < 0.001$).

In children from the comparison group, an increase in IL4 was noted by 7.1 times ($P < 0.01$) in relation to the control group. We also found that in children with community-acquired pneumonia from Khorezm, IL4 increases by 3.8 times compared to children living in Tashkent ($P < 0.01$).

Conclusions:

1. An imbalance of the cytokine status in children with community-acquired pneumonia, expressed by an increase in the levels of IL-1 β , IL-4, IL-6 and TNF α , was revealed, which contributes to the development of hemorrhagic syndrome and serves as an additional criterion for assessing the prognosis of this complication.

2. The severity of the pathoimmunological imbalance in the cytokine status is observed among children with community-acquired pneumonia living in an unfavorable ecological region.

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